

Automated Subject Description for Cultural Heritage and Scientific Data – Between Bibliodata and Information Extraction

The recommendations following Bibliodata WG's *Mutual learning...* workshop

This statement presents the outcome of the [Mutual learning workshop for improving cultural heritage bibliographical data](#) organised by the Bibliographical Data Working Group of DARIAH-ERIC in October 2022.¹ Its main aim was to investigate the relationships between the bibliographical metadata collections and full text collections from national libraries and scientific resources. The need to deepen the understanding of cross-sectoral challenges in the bibliographical data was emphasised in the 2022 WG's report [An Analysis of the Current Bibliographical Data Landscape in the Humanities](#) and this paper implements the recommendations from this publication.

The librarian **metadata collections** are continuously **created** mostly in the form of catalogues and bibliographies (e.g. national bibliographies) which contain nowadays millions of records. Simultaneously, thanks to systematic mass **digitisation**, millions of documents are currently available in digitised form with **full text version** and millions of the others are **digital-born and** available e. g. in digital libraries (e.g. Gallica), scientific repositories (e.g. Zenodo) or metadata aggregators (e.g. OpenAIRE). Despite the fact these collections are created for different purposes and by different stakeholders they are important sources of bibliographical data.

Figure 1: Scheme of automated semantic enrichment of librarian and scientific (meta)data

¹ This event is the main output of the project implemented by Bibliographical Data Working Group in 2022-2023 with support of DARIAH-ERIC Consortium within [DARIAH Working Group Funding Scheme](#).

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WG's 2022 workshop was a step in this direction which needs to be continued, scaled up and enriched with quality research and expertise sharing.

Figure 2: Knowledge exchange scheme for automated subject description in bibliographical data landscape

There are already building blocks for future collaboration available, which include initiatives gathered around during the WG's mutual learning workshop: Annif, Newseye or Impresso or OpenAIRE. While Annif and OpenAire's FoS Classification are bringing NLP techniques into the bibliographical data processing workflows, Newseye and Impresso projects developed tools for semantic enrichment of raw OCR-texts.

Based on the outcomes of the WG's workshop we recommend to scale up and intensify cross-sectoral knowledge exchange related to subject information extraction that would lead to:

- Improved **semantic interoperability** of the results of subject description, e.g. through implementation of interoperable controlled vocabularies,
- Improved **sharing of data science and IT tools** under **open** licences and with state-of-the-art **documentation**,
- Improved **sharing of information extraction workflows** to foster reproducibility and reusability, e.g. through publishing them via [SSH Open Marketplace](#).

Links:

[Workshop program](#)

[Workshop presentations in Zenodo](#)

[Workshop recordings](#)